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«FRACTURE MECHANICS OF MATERIALS
AND STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY»

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The topics of the Conference include the actual problems of Fracture and Strength of Materials, Environmentally Assisted Cracking, Non-Destructive Evaluation, Applied Mechanics and others.

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CONTENTS

FRACTURE AND STRENGTH OF MATERIALS	15
Development of investigations on fracture mechanics of materials and structural integrity: achievements and perspectives <i>Volodymyr PANASYUK</i>	17
The mechanism for counteracting cracking of high-manganese steels with austenitic structure <i>Leszek A. DOBRZANSKI</i>	19
Fracture mechanics study of cementitious materials reinforced with carbon nanotubes and nanofibers <i>Emmanuel E. GDOUTOS, Maria S. KONSTA-GDOUTOS</i>	21
Crack propagation sensitivity index of quasistatic and cyclic loaded engineering structures <i>Laszlo TOTH</i>	23
To the problem of the subsurface defects detection: theory and experiment <i>Zinovyj NAZARCHUK, Leonid MURAVSKY, Dozyslav KURYLIK</i>	25
Application of the theory of large deformation in uniaxial - compression <i>Andrzej KUREK, Justyna KOZIARSKA, Tadeusz ŁAGODA, Karolina ŁAGODA</i> ...	28
Electrodynamic treatment (EDT) of welded joints by electric current pulses as an effective method for regulation of their stressed-strain states <i>Leonid LOBANOV, Nikolai PASHCHIN</i>	29
Influence of the inclusion shape and the constraints level on damage to the elementary cell <i>Jaroslaw GALKIEWICZ</i>	31
Peculiarities of the crack initiation and propagation in different specimen types <i>Eugene KONDRYAKOV, Olexandr PANASENKO, Andriy KRAVCHYK, Valeriy KHARCHENKO</i>	33
Stress-strain analysis of thin-walled structures of complex geometrical shape and prediction of destructive loads <i>Roman KUSHNIR, Bogdan DROBENKO, Mykhaylo MARCHUK</i>	35

Mixed mode (I+II, I+III) fatigue crack growth description in S355/P355NL1 steel	
<i>Grzegorz LESIUK, Dariusz ROZUMEK, Jose A.F.O. CORREIA, Mieczysław SZATA, Abilio M.P. De JESUS</i>	37
Numerical analyses of biomass reinforced composite bridging element	
<i>Róbert BELEZNAI, Zoltán SIMÉNFALVI, Gábor L. SZEPESI</i>	38
Influence of stress ratio on functional fatigue of pseudoelastic NiTi alloy	
<i>Volodymyr IASNII, Petro YASNIY</i>	40
Influence of the atmosphere corrosion on the fatigue life of welded T-joints treated by high frequency mechanical impact	
<i>Vitalii KNYSH, Sergii SOLOVEI, Lyudmila NYRKOVA, Ilyya KLOCHKOV, Sviatoslav MOTRUNICH</i>	42
Determination of GTN parameters of SENT specimen during ductile fracture	
<i>Yassine CHAHBOUB, Szavai SZABOLCS, Zoltan BEZI</i>	44
Influence of a local distributions of stress and strain before tip of a crack at mechanisms of fracture of HARDOX-400 steel	
<i>Ihor DZIOBA, Robert PAŁA</i>	46
Effect of the structure on the mechanical properties and cracking resistance of welded joints of low-alloyed high-strength steels	
<i>Olena BERDNIKOVA, Valery POZNIAKOV, Artemii BERNATSKYI, Tetiana ALEKSEIENKO, Volodymyr SYDORETS</i>	48
Evolution of the mechanical fields and fracture process of S355JR steel	
<i>Ihor DZIOBA, Sebastian LIPIEC</i>	50
Strength of welded joints made of high-strength steel with different welding parameters	
<i>Ihor DZIOBA, Tadeusz PAŁA</i>	52
Short crack problem in delayed fracture mechanics	
<i>Yuri LAPUSTA, Olexandr ANDREIKIV, Nataliya YADZHAK</i>	54
ENVIRONMENTALLY ASSISTED CRACKING	57
<hr/>	
Main factors causing stress corrosion cracking & hydrogen-induced cracking. Gaping in our understanding	
<i>Mimoun ELBOUJDAINI</i>	59
Specific effects of hydrogen concentration on resistance to fracture of ferrite-pearlitic pipeline steels	
<i>Ihor DMYTRAKH, Andriy SYROTYUK, Rostyslav LESHCHAK</i>	60

Assessment of in-service degradation of gas pipeline steel taking into account susceptibility to stress corrosion cracking <i>Olha ZVIRKO, Giovanna GABETTA, Oleksandr TSYRULNYK, Nataliia KRET</i>	62
The energy approach to the evaluation of hydrogen effect on the damage accumulation <i>Yaroslav IVANYTSKYI, Yevhen KHARCHENKO, Oksana HEMBARA, Olha CHEPIL, Yaroslav SAPUZHAK, Nazar HEMBARA</i>	64
Hydrogen assisted crack initiation and propagation in nickel-cobalt heat resistant superalloys <i>Aleksander BALITSKII</i>	66
Developmental strategy for environmentally assisted cracking resistance of copper containing 7xxx series <i>M. Ajay KRISHNAN and V.S. RAJA</i>	68
Influence of the gas hydrates on the rate of corrosion of pipeline <i>Lubomyr POBEREZHZNY, Andrii HRYTSANCHUK, H. GRYTSYLIK</i>	70
Prediction of the residual lifetime of gas pipelines considering the effect of soil corrosion and material degradation <i>Ivan SHTOYKO, Jesus TORIBIO, Viktor KHARIN, Myroslava HREDIL</i>	73
Features of stress corrosion cracking of degraded gas pipeline steels <i>Hryhoriy NYKYFORCHYN, Halyna KRECHKOVSKA, Oleksandra STUDENT, Olha ZVIRKO</i>	75
NON-DESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION	77
<hr/>	
Role and importance of NDE in nuclear power plant life extension <i>Peter TRAMPUS</i>	79
Method of acoustic emission in delayed fracture mechanics of structural materials <i>Zinoviy NAZARCHUK, Olexandr ANDREYKIV, Valentyn SKALSKYY, Denys RUDAVSKYY</i>	80
AE technology in continuous monitoring of high-temperature pipelines at heating power plants <i>Borys PATON, Leonid LOBANOV, Anatoly NEDOSEKA, Stanislav NEDOSEKA, Mihail YAREMENKO, Janos GEREB, Yuri GLADYSHEV, Vadim BESHUN, Alexandr BYCHKOV, Alexandr GAIDUKEVICH</i>	82
Monitoring of the wear of aircraft transmission toothed wheels by the FAM-C and FDM-A methods <i>Andrzej GĘBURA, Sylwester KŁYSZ, Tomasz TOKARSKI</i>	84

Development of electromagnetic NDT methods for structural integrity assessment <i>Valentyn UCHANIN, Orest OSTASH</i>	86
The String Model: a new interpretation of the metallic structures and its connected physical phenomena <i>Giuseppe NARDONI, Ward RUMMEL, Peter TRAMPUS</i>	88
Determination of residual stresses by laser shearography method <i>Leonid LOBANOV, Viktor SAVITSKY</i>	89
Detection of cracks in ferrous steel structures: new innovative eddy current techniques <i>Valentyn UCHANIN, Giuseppe NARDONI</i>	91
Analysis of rotary mechanism fault features on the base of the spectral structure for vibration stochastic recurrence <i>Ihor JAVORSKYJ, Roman YUZEFOVYCH, Pavlo SEMENOV, Pavlo KURAPOV</i>	93
The methodology of evaluation and monitoring of the fatigue fracture at macrocrack initiation stage <i>Roman CHEPIL, Olena STANKEVYCH, Orest OSTASH, Bohdan KLYM</i>	95
Determination of components of transient resistance of underground pipeline <i>Roman DZHALA, Vasyly' DZHALA, Roman SAVULA, Oleh SENYUK, Bohdan VERBENETS'</i>	97
WORKSHOP ON APPLIED MECHANICS	99
<hr/>	
Research progress and prospect of laser hybrid manufacturing technology <i>Jianhua YAO, Volodymyr KOVALENKO</i>	101
Features of the estimation of the influence of various factors on the integrity of the RPV reactor under the action of a melt of metals during a severe accident <i>A.A. KOTLIARENKO, A.Yu. CIRKOV, V.V. KHARCHENKO</i>	102
Effect of carbon nanotubes on the properties of ceramic coating prepared by sol-gel combined laser cladding <i>Qunli ZHANG, Zhongzhi YAO, Jianhua YAO</i>	104
Research on porous structure of the implant <i>Chunyan YAO, Zhongli ZHENG, Wei ZHANG, Yunfeng LIU</i>	106

Surface morphology analysis and wettability of steel and glass modified with graphene oxide <i>Barbara NASIŁOWSKA, Klaudia OLKOWICZ, Aneta BOMBALSKA</i>	108
Effects of high-frequency vibration on the microstructure and tensile property in laser cladding of SS316L alloy <i>Zhehe YAO, Xiaowen YU, Jianhua YAO</i>	110
Influence of gas flow on oxidation of molten pool during laser remelting under open-air condition <i>Gaolin YANG, Jianhua YAO, Zhengting YE</i>	111
Fracture behavior of dissimilar welding of Inconel 600 <i>Teresita SÁNCHEZ CRUZ, Sebastian JAUREGUIZAHAR, Heriberto GRANADOS BECERRA, Victor HUGO LÓPEZ MORELOS, Orest BILYY, Jorge GONZÁLEZ-SÁNCHEZ</i>	113
Advanced deposition characteristics of diamond-reinforced Cu matrix composite coating by supersonic laser deposition <i>Lijuan WU, Jianhua YAO, Bo LI, Weilin WANG, Xuanjie HUANG, Qunli ZHANG</i>	115
Consideration of the effect of biaxial loading and short cracks on RPV steel fracture toughness <i>V. G. SIDYACHENKO, A. A. KOTLIARENKO</i>	116
Study on laser cladding Fe-based wear resistant coating on inner wall <i>Jianhua YAO, Zhongyao CAI, Zhijun CHEN, Volodymyr KOVALENKO</i>	118
Role of in-service conditions in operational degradation of mechanical properties of portal cranes steel <i>Oleksiy NEMCHUK, Myroslava HREDIL, Vitaliy PUSTOVOY, Oleksandr NESTEROV</i>	120
Influence of pipeline steel texture on macro- and micromechanisms of its impact fracture <i>Yevstakhiy KRYZHANIVSKYY, Liubomyr POBEREZHNY, Pavlo MARUSCHAK, Mykhailo LYAKH, Volodymyr SLOBODYAN, Vasył ZAPUKHLIAK</i>	122
Effect of the application of an external magnetic field during the process of fusing welding in stainless steel duplex 2205 in the resistance to cracking by corrosion fatigue <i>Alexandro De LEÓN, Jorge GONZÁLEZ-SANCHEZ, Orest BILYY</i>	124
Qualimetric analysis of pipelines with surface corrosion defects <i>Roman DZHALA, Volodymyr YUZEVYCH, Vitalii LOZOVAN, Andriy MYTSYK, Ruslan SKRYNKOVSKYY, Mykhailo YASINSKYI</i>	125

Microcrack under internal pressure at dislocation defect <i>Mykola STASHCHUK, Nataliya HEMBARA, Vitalii KOVALCHUK</i>	127
Corrosion of drill pipes in high mineralized formation waters <i>Igor CHUDYK, Lyubomyr POBEREZHNY, Andrii HRYTSANCHUK, Liubov POBEREZHNA</i>	129
Requirements for hydrogen resistance of materials in CI engine toxic substances powered by biofuels <i>Jacek Jaroslaw ELIASZ, Alexander BALITSKII, Tomasz OSIPOWICZ, Karol Franciszek ABRAMEK</i>	131

QUALIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF PIPELINES WITH SURFACE CORROSION DEFECTS

Roman Dzhala¹, Volodymyr Yuzevych^{1*}, Vitalii Lozovan¹,
Andriy Mytsyk², Ruslan Skrynkovskyy³, Mykhailo Yasinskyi⁴

¹ *Karpenko Physico-Mechanical Institute of NASU, Ukraine*

² *Public Joint-Stock Company "UKRTRANSNAZ" – Affiliate "Lvivtransgaz", Ukraine*

³ *Lviv University of Business and Law, Ukraine*

⁴ *Ukrainian Academy of Printing, Ukraine*

* *Presenting Author: yuzevych@ukr.net*

Keywords: pipeline; metal; structure degradation; fracture; cavity; crack; metrology; quality control; non-destructive control.

The possibility of assessing the quality of underground metal pipelines (UMP) with corrosion defects on the basis of control of defect parameters with the use of computer technologies that allow to model the monitoring of measurement processes as well as aspects of degradation and destruction of pipes is shown.

To solve the task of assessing the resource of an underground metal pipeline it is important to properly organize the monitoring of properties, which allows you to get information about the actual processes and the state of the object. According to the results of the monitoring, we conduct an assessment and analysis of the characteristics of the processes, as well as a statistical analysis of the causes of the deviations of parameters. For the solution of these tasks data on the electrophysical parameters of the pipe and the environment are required. We study variations of various controlled parameters and variants of their influence on the pipelines quality characteristics.

Taking into account the relations of surface physics and fracture mechanics, a mathematical model [1] was constructed for the evaluation of parameters characterizing the mechanical state of the metal in the vicinity of the cavern peak at which the crack is continued (Fig. 1). Using the experimental values p_{cr} of the yield boundary, the depths of the cavity and the crack, a critical value of the internal pressure p_{cr} was calculated, in which at the top of the crack a zone of plastic deformation p_{cr1} and the critical state p_{cr2} (fracture) are emerged [2]. The values of p_{cr1} and p_{cr2} are obtained and are important parameters for assessing the strength and life of the pipeline under the influence of external corrosive media.

Fig. 1. Pipe with corrosion cavity and crack in the electrolyte
 (p – pressure; σ_0 – ring mechanical stresses; c – crack depth).

The information necessary to evaluate the conditions for degradation of the structure and the destruction of underground metal pipes and, consequently, the quality of the pipeline, is established on the basis of the analysis of electrical currents and voltages obtained by contactless current meter (CCM) and a polarization potential meter (PPM).

In the same way as in [3], the multiplicative and qualimetric criterion for the UMP area will be presented as:

$$Z_1 = \prod_{i=1}^m k_i = k_1 \cdot k_2 \cdot k_3 \cdot k_4 \cdot k_5 \cdot k_6 \cdot k_7 \cdot k_8 \cdot k_9 \Rightarrow \max, \quad (1)$$

where k_1 – coefficient of level of metrological support UMP; k_2 – coefficient of reliability level UMP; k_3 – coefficient characterizing the strength of the metal p_S UMP; $k_4(D_f)$, $k_5(n_z, \Delta K_{th})$, $k_6(\sigma_{ve})$, $k_7(K_S)$, $k_8(T_S, N_C)$, $k_9(U_P)$ – coefficients that characterize the defect D_f , strengthening n_z , the limit of corrosion fatigue $\sigma_{ve}(N_C)$, the effect of the coating on corrosion resistance K_S , the term of trouble-free work T_S (resource) structures (pipes) taking into account N_C ; observance of the optimal range of polarization potential U_P ; N_C – number of load cycles.

On the basis of the results we evaluate the reliability and residuality of the resource in the underground pipeline.

References

1. Yuzevych V.M., Dzhala R.M., Koman B.P. Analysis of Metal Corrosion under Conditions of Mechanical Impacts and Aggressive Environments. *Metallofizika i Noveishie Tekhnologii* 12 (2018) 1655–1667.
2. Dzhala R.M., Savula S.F., Yuzevych V.M. The mathematical model for estimating the resource of a pipeline with a corrosion crack under pressure of internal pressure. *Methods and instruments of control* 4 (33) (2014) 123–126.
3. Lozovan V., Dzhala R., Skrynkovskyy R., Yuzevych V. Detection of specific features in the functioning of a system for the anti-corrosion protection of underground pipelines at oil and gas enterprises using neural networks. *Eastern-European J. of Enterprise Technologies* 1/5 (97) (2019) 20–27.

AVTORS INDEX

- Abramek K. F.* 131
Alekseienko T. 48
Andreikiv O. 54, 80
Balitskii A. 66, 131
Beleznai R. 38
Berdnikova O. 48
Bernatskyi A. 48
Beshun V. 82
Bezi Z. 44
Bilyy O. 113, 124
Bombalska A. 108
Bychkov A. 82
Cai Zhongyao 118
Chahboub Ya. 44
Chen Zhijun 118
Chepil O. 64
Chepil R. 95
Chudyk I. 129
Cirkov A. Yu. 102
Correia Jose A.F.O. 37
De Jesus Abilio M. P. 37
De Leon A. 124
Dmytrakh I. 60
Dobrzanski L. A. 19
Drobenko B. 35
Dzhala R. 97, 125
Dzhala V. 97
Dzioba I. 46, 50, 52
Elboujdaini M. 59
Eliasz J. J. 131
Gabetta G. 62
Gaidukevich A. 82
Galkiewicz J. 31
Gdoutos E. E. 21
Gebura A. 84
Gereb J. 82
Gladyshev Yu. 82
Gonzalez-Sanchez J. 113, 124
Granados Becerra H. 113
Grytsyliak H. 70
Hembara Nataliya 127
Hembara Nazar 64
Hembara O. 64
Hredil M. 73, 120
Hrytsanchuk A. 70, 129
Huang Xuanjie 115
Hugo Lopez Morelos V. 113
Iasnii V. 40
Ivanytskyi Y. 64
Jaureguizar S. 113
Javorskyj I. 93
Kharchenko V. 33, 102
Kharchenko Ye. 64
Kharin V. 73
Klochkov I. 42
Klym B. 95
Klysz S. 84
Knysh V. 42
Kondryakov E. 33
Konsta-Gdoutos M. S. 21
Kotliarenko A. A. 102, 116
Kovalchuk V. 127
Kovalenko V. 101, 118
Koziarska J. 28
Kravchyk A. 33
Krechkovska H. 75
Kret N. 62
Krishnan M. A. 68
Kryzhanivsky Y. 122
Kurapov P. 93
Kurek A. 28
Kuryliak D. 25
Kushnir R. 35
Lagoda K. 28

<i>Lagoda T.</i>	28	<i>Semenov P.</i>	93
<i>Lapusta Yu.</i>	54	<i>Senyuk O.</i>	97
<i>Leshchak R.</i>	60	<i>Shtoyko I.</i>	73
<i>Lesiuk G.</i>	37	<i>Sidyachenko V. G.</i>	116
<i>Li Bo</i>	115	<i>Simenfalvi Z.</i>	38
<i>Lipiec S.</i>	50	<i>Skalskyy V.</i>	80
<i>Liu Yunfeng</i>	106	<i>Skrynkovskyy R.</i>	125
<i>Lobanov L.</i>	29, 82, 89	<i>Slobodyan V.</i>	122
<i>Lozovan V.</i>	125	<i>Solovei S.</i>	42
<i>Lyakh M.</i>	122	<i>Stankevych O.</i>	95
<i>Marchuk M.</i>	35	<i>Stashchuk M.</i>	127
<i>Maruschak P.</i>	122	<i>Student O.</i>	75
<i>Motrunich S.</i>	42	<i>Sydorets V.</i>	48
<i>Muravsky L.</i>	25	<i>Syrotyuk A.</i>	60
<i>Mytsyk A.</i>	125	<i>Szabolcs S.</i>	44
<i>Nardoni G.</i>	88, 91	<i>Szata M.</i>	37
<i>Nasilowska B.</i>	108	<i>Szepesi G. L.</i>	38
<i>Nazarchuk Z.</i>	25, 80	<i>Tokarski T.</i>	84
<i>Nedoseka A.</i>	82	<i>Toribio J.</i>	73
<i>Nedoseka S.</i>	82	<i>Toth L.</i>	23
<i>Nemchuk O.</i>	120	<i>Trampus P.</i>	79, 88
<i>Nesterov O.</i>	120	<i>Tsyurulnyk O.</i>	62
<i>Nykyforchyn H.</i>	75	<i>Uchanin V.</i>	86, 91
<i>Nyrkova L.</i>	42	<i>Verbenets' B.</i>	97
<i>Olkowicz K.</i>	108	<i>Wang Weilin</i>	115
<i>Osipowicz T.</i>	131	<i>Wu Lijuan</i>	115
<i>Ostash O.</i>	86, 95	<i>Yadzhak N.</i>	54
<i>Pala R.</i>	46	<i>Yang Gaolin</i>	111
<i>Pala T.</i>	52	<i>Yao Chunyan</i>	106
<i>Panasenko O.</i>	33	<i>Yao Jianhua</i>	101, 104, 110, 111, 115, 118
<i>Panasyuk V.</i>	17	<i>Yao Zhehe</i>	110
<i>Pashchin N.</i>	29	<i>Yao Zhongzhi</i>	104
<i>Paton B.</i>	82	<i>Yaremenko M.</i>	82
<i>Poberezhna L.</i>	129	<i>Yasynskiy M.</i>	125
<i>Poberezhny L.</i>	70, 122, 129	<i>Yasniy P.</i>	40
<i>Pozniakov V.</i>	48	<i>Ye Zhengting</i>	111
<i>Pustovoy V.</i>	120	<i>Yu Xiaowen</i>	110
<i>Raja V. S.</i>	68	<i>Yuzefovych R.</i>	93
<i>Rozumek D.</i>	37	<i>Yuzevych V.</i>	125
<i>Rudavskyy D.</i>	80	<i>Zapukhliak V.</i>	122
<i>Rummel W.</i>	88	<i>Zhang Qunli</i>	104, 115
<i>Sanchez Cruz T.</i>	113	<i>Zhang Wei</i>	106
<i>Sapuzhak Y.</i>	64	<i>Zheng Zhongli</i>	106
<i>Savitsky V.</i>	89	<i>Zvirko O.</i>	62, 75
<i>Savula R.</i>	97		

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